

OIL FROM THE SEEDS OF *BOMBAX MALABARICUM*

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The oil from the seeds of *Bombax malabaricum* contains 94.8% insoluble mixed fatty acids composed of 57% of solid acids and 43% of liquid acids. The composition of the fatty acids is found to be 1.2% myristic acid, 23.6% palmitic acid, 2.8% arachidic acid, 64.9% oleic acid and 7.5% linoleic acid. The seed cake is found to contain 34.4% of crude protein.

Bombax malabaricum belonging to the family of *Bombacaceae* is an evergreen tree found in the forest areas in India.

The Kapok, usually mentioned as white silk cotton and red silk cotton, has its origin from distinct genera *Buonopozenne* (*Eriodendron anfractuosum*) and *Bombax malabaricum*.

Earlier work on the subject deals with the characteristics of Kapok oil without reference to the particular species (Lewkowitsch "Technology and Analysis of Oils, Fats and Waxes", Vol. II, p. 186; *Bull. Imp. Inst.*, 1926, 24, 18). Georgi (*Malay Agric. J.*, 1922, 10, 284) determined the constants of the oil obtained from the seed of *Eriodendron* species. Latest work done by Mehlebacher (*Oil & Soap*, 1937, 14, 118) refers to analysis of a sample of refined Kapok oil obtained from Japan. He detected the presence of oleic and linoleic acids in the oil.

As the information on the various constituents of the oil from the seeds of *Bombax malabaricum* is very meagre and a few characterisations found for the oil appear in the common name of Kapok, systematic investigation on the fatty acid composition of the oil was undertaken and the results recorded in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

The seeds of *Bombax malabaricum* were collected in the months of April and May, 1942 from the Parvatipur Agency tract, Vizagapatam, Madras Presidency and the powdered seed on extraction with carbon tetrachloride gave 26% of a dark yellow oil having the physical and chemical characteristics given in Tables I and II along with the figures of analysis of the previous workers.

The present sample has a lower iodine value compared to the sample reported by Sprinkmeyer which might be due to the climatic conditions (*Chem. Umchau*, 1929, 36, 40). Maumene test indicates that the oil is a non-drying oil which is further corroborated by its low iodine value. The present sample has a high acid value (32.58% as oleic acid), which might be due to the fact that the seeds collected in May were crushed and extracted in December. The oil also develops acidity very rapidly since the value increases from 32.58 to 42.16 in six months. High acid value indicates the ease with which it becomes rancid due to decomposition. This rapid decomposition makes it unsuitable as a frying fat for edible purposes due to the acrid taste and bad odour imparted to the articles fried in this oil. It is noticeable that the acidity increases at a fairly rapid rate, presumably because of the free acid acting as a catalyst to accelerate the reaction.

TABLE I

Analysis of the seed

	Present workers (Bombay).	Bull. Imp. Institute, (Kopok seed oil).	Georgi (<i>Eriodendron anfractuosum</i>).	
Ash % seeds	5.16	—	—	M. p.
Oil % seeds	26	22.3	19.4 to 24.4	S. p.
Protein % seed cake	34.4	36	24.88	Sp. gr.
Hull % seeds	45	—	43.2	Ref. Index
Kernel % seeds	55	—	56.8	Sap. V.

TABLE II

Analysis of the oil

	Present workers (Bombay).	Lewkowitch Vol. II Sprinkmeyer (Bombay).	Georgi (<i>Eriodendron anfractuosum</i>).	Mehlenbacher (Kopok oil, Japan.)
	34°	—	—	—
	30°	—	—	—
	0.9362 at 35°	0.9236 at 15°	0.928 at 15.5°	0.920 at 15°
	1.4611 at 40°	59.7 at 40° Oleo-ref. reading	na 20-1.4685 1.4710	57.6 at 40° (Butyro ref. reading)
	196.3	194.5	191-193.3	191.2
	68.12	93.78	94.3-98.1	100.5
	32.58% as oleic acid	—	1.8-26.9%	26.8
	1.761%	—	8-1.16%	—
	94.8%	95.66	—	—
	133.3	—	—	—
(b) Mixed acids				
	274.5	—	284.3-292.4	—
	71.78	98.9	94.2-96.6	—

Component Fatty Acids

300 G. of the oil were saponified with strong alcoholic soda. The acids liberated from the soap were resolved into solid and liquid acids according to Twitchell's lead-salt-alcohol method (Twitchell, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1921, 13, 806) and converted into their methyl esters. The physical and chemical properties of the acids and their esters are given below.

TABLE III

	% on oil.	Sap. equiv.	I. V.	Fr. No.	Temp. bath.	Temp. frac.	Wt. of frac.	Sap. equiv.	L.V.	Identification.
Oil	100	285.8	68.2	S ₁	190-195°	136-144°	10.4 g.	278.9	31.2	Oleic and palmitic
Mixed acids	94.8	274.5	71.80	S ₂	195-200°	144-145°	35.5	283.7	47.70	" "
(S) Solid acids	54	273.5	53.1	S ₃	200-205°	145°	18.9	288.9	67.60	" "
(L) Liquid acids	40.8	278.9	96.9	S ₄	205-225°	145-156°	12.7	296.7	61.80	" "
(S) Solid esters	—	286.8	50.6	S ₅	(Residue)	—	7.5	296.8	34.20	" "
(L) Liquid esters	—	293.8	92.29	—	—	—	—	—	—	" "

TABLE IV

Fractionation of solid esters

(Wt = 85 g.) Sp. Eq. 286.8, I.V. = 50.6.

	% on oil.	Sap. equiv.	I. V.	Fr. No.	Temp. bath.	Temp. frac.	Wt. of frac.	Sap. equiv.	L.V.	Identification.
Oil	100	285.8	68.2	S ₁	190-195°	136-144°	10.4 g.	278.9	31.2	Oleic and palmitic
Mixed acids	94.8	274.5	71.80	S ₂	195-200°	144-145°	35.5	283.7	47.70	" "
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(L) Liquid acids	40.8	278.9	96.9	S ₄	205-225°	145-156°	12.7	296.7	61.80	" "
(S) Solid esters	—	286.8	50.6	S ₅	(Residue)	—	7.5	296.8	34.20	" "
(L) Liquid esters	—	293.8	92.29	—	—	—	—	—	—	" "

Methyl esters were fractionally distilled at 2 mm. using Willstätter's bulb and the data given in Table IV. .

TABLE V

Fractionation of the liquid esters

(Wt. = 64 g.) Sap. equiv. 293.2, I.V. = 92.19.

Frac. No.	Bath temp.	Frac. temp.	Frac. wt.	Sap. equiv	I. V.	Identification.
L ₁	190-195°	99-144°	12.8	285.8	65.50	Oleic, myristic and palmitic.
L ₂	195-200°	144°	13.8	292	95.80	Oleic, linoleic and palmitic
L ₃	200-215°	144-150°	19.5	293.3	110.5	„ „
L ₄	215-230°	150-156°	9.8	295.5	91.80	Oleic and linoleic.
Residue			8.1	302.6*	87.90	Oleic and linoleic and non saponifiable matter.

* Corr. value = 295.8

Myristic acid (m.p. 52°), palmitic acid (m.p. 62°) and arachidic acid (m.p. 75°) were identified from the various fractions by mixed melting points with authentic samples. Methyl arachidate melted at 52-53°. The unsaturated acids were identified by oxidation with alkaline permanganate (Lapworth and Mottram, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 1628), when dihydroxystearic acid (m.p. 150°) and tetrahydroxystearic acid (m.p. 170-71°) were obtained confirming the presence of oleic and linoleic acids.

Oleic and linoleic acids were further identified by bromination by the method of Eibner and Muganthalder and this indicated the absence of linolenic acid as no hexabromide could be isolated.

From the above identifications the acids are calculated on percentage basis and given below along with the fatty acid composition of cotton seed oil.

TABLE VI

Acids	Solid 57%	Liquid 43%	Total acids (% by wt.)	Mol. %	*Cotton seed oil, I.V. = 105
Myristic	—	1.2	1.2	1.45	2.3
Palmitic	20.3	3.3	23.6	25.40	24.5
Stearic	—	—	—	—	1.1
Arachidic	2.8	—	2.6	2.50	0.5
Oleic	33.9	31.0	64.9	63.30	22.5
Linoleic	—	7.5	7.5	7.40	46.5
Tetradecenoic	—	—	—	—	0.2
Hexadecenoic	—	—	—	—	2.2
			100.0	100.00	99.8

Association ratio = 2.41

* Hilditch and Maddison, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1940, 58, 1127.

C O N C L U S I O N S

The fatty oil contains 1'2% myristic acid, 23'6% palmitic acid, 2'8% arachidic acid, 64'9% oleic acid and 7'5% linoleic acid. The presence of even traces of stearic acid could not be found.

The seed cake after extraction of the oil is found to contain 34'4% of crude protein, and the ash contains potash. Though adverse reports are made as regards its use as cattle food it should serve as a rich manure.

As the oil develops rapidly free acidity up to 40%, the glyceride structure could not be determined.

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